

USER AWARENESS AND USE OF ELECTRONIC JOURNALS: A STUDY

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Abstract

The advancement in information technology has changed the reading habits and the publication format of documents. E-journal is a well established and the most popular phenomena. The present paper deals with the awareness and use of e-journals by researchers. The study reviled the purpose of using e-journals, frequency of use, location of accessing e-journals, using patron and satisfaction level of users

Introduction

Library is a metaphor of the memory of mankind. Information and communication technologies, the Internet and the web have given rise to a situation where we are having more and more of data but less and less of information and knowledge on the web. Barring the commercial domain, there is a lot of chaos on the web in the Public domain. Rapid cycle of innovation and obsolescence has made our job more difficult and challenging. New formats of information communication are appearing in the digital environment like e – books, e-journals etc. E-journals are also well-established phenomena.

E-journal

E-Journal is a digital version of a print journal, or a journal-like electronic publication with no print counterpart (example: First Monday,

Webology), made available via the Web, e-mail, or other means of Internet access. Some Web-based electronic journals are graphically modeled on the print version. The rising cost of print journal subscriptions has led many academic libraries to explore electronic alternatives.

Review of the related literature

Chandra (2006) gives a brief introduction about the building e-collection in libraries and their features. It also discusses the e-books and e-journals, their utility, features, advantages, factors for the selection. The paper further narrates the experience with screenshots for providing access to e-books and e-journals at IIT Madras under intranet and the Internet with the help of central Library website. This usage statistics and selected e-journal publishers and gateways are also listed.

Nikam and Pramodini (2007) describe the use of e-journals and data bases by the users of University of Mysore. Nearly 200 responses to a survey based on questionnaire have been analyzed and presented by the authors. The paper also examines the utilization and satisfaction levels of users with respect to the e-resources.

Dilek-Kayaogly's (2008) study focused on use of e journals by faculty of Istanbul University, Turkey. The majority of respondents of survey supported the transition from print to e-only. Some respondents reported that the major barrier to use e-journals was the lack of subscriptions in their field.

Kumber and Gururaj (2009) revealed that 88.09% faculty members and 93.33% research scholars felt the necessity to include more e-journals in the current consortium programme. 81.66% research scholars and 64.29% faculty members felt the need of regular training programmes. The study revealed that 27.45% respondents found UGC-InfoNet e-journal programme as excellent. 66.67% faculty and 70% research scholars preferred both electronic as well as

print version of journals. Almost half of the faculty members (47.61%) and a little more than half of research scholars (61.66%) felt that the information content available in e-journals is better than the printed version.

Objectives of the study

- To ascertain awareness and acceptance of e-journals.
- To explore the use of electronic journals.
- To study the purpose of utilization of e-journals.
- To ascertain the frequency of using e-journals.
- To study the preferred format for using e-journals.
- To study the satisfaction level of users.

Scope and Methodology

The present study deals with the use of electronic journals. The scope of the study is to examine the awareness of the researchers of the universities regarding the e-journals. The study has been confined to the users of the e-journals at Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar. During the 500 year of birth of Sri Guru Nanak Dev Ji in 1969, it was decided to set up a university in his name. The Guru Nanak Dev University came into being on November 24, 1969 under act 21 of the Punjab Government. Spread over a stretch of 500 acres towards the west of the city, Guru Nanak Dev University presents a picture of modern architecture. It is highly innovative in designing its teaching and research programmes and offers a comprehensive range of general and applied courses. At present, nearly 5000 students are studying on the Campus, All India Services Training Centre, Instrumentation Centre, Computer Centre, 24 hour internet facility, Placement Unit etc. To promote research among its faculty, almost all the Departments have been provided with independent computer facilities, internet connectivity and departmental libraries. Over the years, the University has built up an excellent academic infrastructure in the form of a well-stocked library, state-of-the-art laboratories, Academic Staff.

Keeping in view the scope and area of the study, a structured questionnaire was prepared to collect the data from the users accessing e-journals available online at Punjabi university of Patiala, relating to various disciplines. The questionnaire contained relevant questions pertaining to awareness with respect to e-journals. For this purpose a total of 70 questionnaires were distributed among Ph.D. researchers. Out of those 70 questionnaires, 68 valid questionnaires were collected and then data was analyzed, tabulated, interpreted and graphically represented in this paper.

Results

Population Study

Table 1: Population studied

Gender	Number	
	Distributed	Received
Male	40 (57.14%)	40 (58.8%)
Female	30 (42.86%)	28 (41.2%)

The table shows the gender difference between the researchers studied. 58.8% male responses are studied and 41.2% of the total female responses are studied, who accessed e-journals available through the Internet.

Awareness about e-journals

Table 2: Awareness of e-journals

Gender	Aware	Not Aware
Male	37 (92.5%)	03(07.5%)
Female	22 (78.6%)	06 (21.4%)

Table 2 depicts the awareness relating to e-journals among the researches. 92.5% male researchers are aware about e-journals whereas only

78.6% female researchers are aware about e-journals. It is thus analyzed that male researchers are more aware than their counterpart.

Preference level

The result reveals that 41.2% of researchers would like to access only the electronic version of the journals whereas 11.8% researchers prefers at reading the printed version of the journals. But 47% researchers are using both the electronic and printed versions of the journals.

Fig. 1: preference level of users

Purpose of using e-journals

Table3: Using Purpose of e-Journal

Purpose	Number	Percentage*
For Research work	68	100
For Writing Paper	39	57.3
Updating Subject Knowledge	24	35.3
For Other Purpose	03	0.04

* More than one responses were allowed to be made for the study

Table 3: shows that all researchers use e-journals for their research work. 57.3% researchers use the e-journals also for the purpose of paper writing. 35.3% researchers use it for updating subject knowledge and a very few (0.04%) researchers use it for other purposes like exam's, etc.

Frequency of use

It is observed from the analysis that four researchers (05.8%) access e-journals every day, 11.8% researchers access 2-3times in a week, 51.5% researchers use it once a week. E-journals are occasionally accessed by 21 researchers (30.9%).

Fig. 2: Using frequency of researchers

Location for accessing e-journals

The study renders that only 07% researchers use the e-journals at the main library of the university. E-journals are accessed in the concerned department by 21% researchers. 56% researchers access e-journals at other places like hostel, research flat, home, etc.

Fig. 3: Using Place

Using Pattern of e-journals

The results shows that the maximum numbers of researchers (35.3%) store the relevant document in their removable storage device. 33.8% users take print of the electronic article for their study. While 30.9% researchers read it on their system's screen.

Fig. 4: Using style of e-journals

Formats of e-journals

There are many formats available to present or publish research paper or article in electronic format. Most researchers (47%) prefer the Portable Document Format (PDF), because it is ready to print, easy to save, standard format, etc. HTML format is also a popular style. 41.2% researchers like this format, because it is easy to read, dynamic in style & colours, ready to read (no downloading required), etc. The image format is also liked by 7.4% researchers. 4.4% researchers have no preference about the format of e-journal.

Fig. 5: Format preferences of e-journals

Satisfaction level

It was observed that majority of researchers are satisfied with the using, style, information presentation and searching style of e-journals. Out of it, 48.5% are highly satisfied and 45.6% are satisfied. Only four researchers (5.9%) are not satisfied with e-journals.

Fig 6: Satisfaction level of users

Conclusion

From the above study it has been observed that e-journals have become a vital part for providing information. E-journals have turned out as a vital knowledge base for our research community. Efficient management of time has been made possible through their usage. Thus the present scenario entails for spreading of awareness among the users and for development of proper infrastructure within the library system to achieve significant results.

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